

The Effects of Averaging within Probability in Quantum Mechanics

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In classical probability, an average is a basis measure of a set of data. We suggest that the set of data is like a vector and that the average reduces this vector to a scalar and thereby loses information. As a result, one often uses the average together with a standard deviation. An average, however, is not the same as a probability, but it does take a vector and reduce it to a scalar.

In quantum mechanics, we suggest that the wavefunction, W , is a vector probability and that the so-called probability of presence or spatial density W^*W is a scalar, i.e. a modulus. In other words, we argue that a kind of averaging has already occurred in creating W^*W which loses much critical information. W^*W is a kind of average probability which only corresponds to an averaging of measurements and does not allow one to solve momentum related physical problems such as 2-slit scattering and one dimensional reflection-refraction. In particular, we note that $\exp(ipx)$ is a 2-vector and $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ a scalar with little information. $\exp(ipx)$ represents a spatial resolution of \hbar/p which is completely lost in 1. Thus, we argue that W^*W is not really a probability of presence.

Averaging may even occur in W . For example, for a bound state, time averaging exists because one uses $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This averaging reveals the resolution peaks/troughs, but a 2-vector is reduced to a single component. Physically, the two vector has not disappeared, it is only averaged down to one. Similarly, classical physics arises by using an envelope function (1) which touches peaks of W^*W and so we argue that this is a kind of blurring process which removes information.

In (1), the notion of W^*W in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics has been extended by using a nonrelativistic limit of a Dirac 4-vector, i.e. has been reduced to two 2-spinors $(W, \sigma \cdot p / 2m W)$ ((1)) where σ are the Pauli matrices. This leads to $W^*W + 1/(4m) \text{grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad} W$ as the "probability of presence", but once again a vector probability, this time a double vector because for a free particle one has $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ linked to each component and so W^*W leads to a double loss of information when taking $W_{\text{total}}^* \cdot W_{\text{total}}$. In particular, for a free particle, the vector form ((1)) retains the resolution \hbar/p even though for $\exp(-ipx)$ the bottom component is phase shifted. Thus, we argue that the vector W is a better representation of probability of presence and that $W^* \cdot W$ is again a kind of averaging which loses information in the problem.

Classical Probability and Averages

Classical probability is a set of positive numbers between which add to 1. It is obtained from data and seems to reveal a frequency associated with specific data points. Thus, taking an average, $\sum_i P(i) i$, takes a set of data (like a vector) and collapses it into a scalar, with the probability simply indicating frequency of i . As a result, much information is lost.

In a classical physical problem, this has consequences on how one views the physical situation. For example, for a classical particle in a box, bouncing back and forth, average momentum is 0. This, however, corresponds to two scenarios. One represents a stationary

particle in the box and the second, a bouncing one. By giving a further piece of information, namely kinetic energy, one may rule out the former. The point is, however, that that average value alone is not sufficient.

In a classical scenario, even if one insists on motion of the particle, one may ask: What is the probability for the particle to be within a certain dx ? If the speed is constant, then Δt is proportional to this value. In the classical world then, such a $P(x)$, together with the value $p^2/2m$, would seem to provide all of the information that one needs ($V(x)=0$) in this case, if one is not interested in whether the particle moves to the right or left. A problem with this description, as we have suggested in previous notes, is that conservation of momentum, which appears in classical physics, must be enforced independently and does not appear as a consequence of probability even though there is a probability of 1 for conservation and 0 for non-conservation as in two particle scattering.

The Quantum Situation

If one suggests that a probabilistic description of a particle moving at constant speed should not only let one know the amount of time spent in each dx , but should also enforce conservation of momentum, then as we have argued in previous notes, one has:

$$\text{Probability} = \exp(ipx) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{such that} \quad \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1 \quad ((3))$$

$((3))$ is the scalar classical probability (unnormalized) of $P(x)$. A more complete probability is the vector $\exp(ipx)$ and $((3))$ is the modulus which reduces the vector to a scalar and involves adding. Like in the case of the classical average, this adding removes information. We suggest that even though $((3))$ seems to give the probability of presence, it completely loses the sense of the wavelength \hbar/p which is critical to probability of presence, because one cannot resolve the presence within a wavelength. This in turn leads to interference in a 2-slit experiment and is also critical to solving the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, which cannot be solved using $P(x)=1/L$, where L is length.

In other words, the classical probability W^*W is an average probability with information removed from the vector probability W .

Using W^*W , which removes vector probability information and so represents an average, is not the only way to create an average probability.

As noted in (1), given a $W^n(x)W_n(x)$ for a bound state, with n , the energy level, being high, one has a set of crests with differing heights and widths. If one creates an envelope function which passes through the peaks, then (1) states that this envelope should be equivalent to $P(x) = C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. $C/v(x)$ is proportional to Δt , the time spent in each dx , and C is a normalization constant. This, we argue, is a different kind of averaging which removes the resolution of the various crests to create a smooth function with infinite x resolution present. In other words, information is being lost through this averaging process.

A New Proposal for Probability of Presence in (2)

In (2), it is suggested that one consider the wavefunction, which is a 4-component object, from Dirac relativistic theory. This may be reduced to two functions each with a 2-spinor. In the nonrelativistic limit, one has (2):

$$W_{\text{total}} = \{ W, \frac{1}{2m} \sigma \cdot p W \} \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } \sigma \text{ is the vector of Pauli matrices}$$

For a free particle, $W = \exp(ip \cdot r)$, or $\exp(ipx)$ for simplicity, which is, itself, a 2 vector. In other words, using the Dirac picture one has a vector in each component of another 2 vector. We note that for the free particle case, $\exp(ipx)$ appears in both components and so the resolution information, \hbar/p , which has physical consequences is intact. For an infinite square well potential, one may see that $\text{grad} \exp(-ipx)$ introduces an extra phase. Nonrelativistically, one would have $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$, but now this only holds for the top component in ((4)), while the bottom component yields $i \sin(px)$. Even though these have the same wavelength, they are phase shifted which means that one takes $W_{\text{total}} \cdot W_{\text{total}}$, one averages in a sense and loses the zeros which were originally present. This does not mean, however, that physically the resolution is gone, we argue. The important probability is W_{total} , we argue, and $W_{\text{total}} \cdot W_{\text{total}}$, just like $W \cdot W$ is an averaged probability which loses much information.

Averaging in W

We suggest that averaging used to create a probability, even W , can lead to a loss of information. For example, for a bound state, one averages in time, including both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This reduces a 2-component vector to one component. One sees the resolution peaks and troughs, but the averaging has lost the physical reality that two components still exist. Thus, one should be cautious of such averaged probabilities when trying to make interpretations. For example, one might say that $W(x)$ -bound has 0 values, but these are only 0 values created by one component of $\exp(ipx)$'s. There is still the second component which has been averaged out, but not physically removed. A particle still moves to the right for some time and then to the left at another time, especially as energy levels increase.

The Case of Orthogonality

For solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation, one has orthogonal $W_n(x)$'s in x for $V(x)$. This is important in calculating transition rates using Born's rule, linked to $\langle W_2 | V | W_1 \rangle = \langle W_2 | V | W_1 \rangle$. If one considers a vector W_{total} ((4)), then for $V(x)=1$, $W_n=1$ and $W_n=2$ etc are no longer necessarily orthogonal. For example, one has:

$$\langle W_{\text{total } n=1} | W_{\text{total } n=2} \rangle = \frac{1}{4m} \int dx \frac{dW_{n=1}}{dx} \frac{dW_{n=2}}{dx} dx \quad ((5))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit, the second component of ((4)) is of the order of v/c for $W^* \text{total} \cdot W^*$ and does not contribute much, i.e. is almost 0.

It is noted in (2), however, that the second component can contribute to removing the resolution seen in W^*W for say a harmonic oscillator. In other words, the second term $1/(4\pi m) dW^*/dx dW/dx$ leads to a more classical looking smooth function instead of one with distinct peaks which have base values dropping to 0. We argue, however, that physically W^*W is a time average which loses physical information, but reveals the peaks (with their 0 endpoint base values) and that this represents physical resolution in the problem. Using $W^* \text{total} \cdot W^* \text{total}$ to remove these simply means that one is using extra averaging to obscure, so to speak, the full information of the wavefunction. We have already noted in a previous note that $W(x)$ using both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ with equal weights or $a(p) = a(-p)$ and this is a kind of averaging which destroys the vector nature of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ leaving only the first or second vector component, i.e. $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, but this does not mean that they physically disappear, they simply average out.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that just as an average in classical probability reduces a vector of data into a single scalar, thus losing much information, so too does W^*W represent the collapsing of a 2-vector into a scalar with also the loss of information. In particular, for a free particle, the vector probability is $\exp(ipx)$ and this represents a physical resolution \hbar/p which is key to describing physical phenomena such as 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction probabilities. By creating W^*W , $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ have different 0 points, although the same wavelengths, but this is completely lost in $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$. Furthermore, even though $P(x)dx = dx/L$ (like $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$), this probability does not include the probability linked with conservation of momentum which may be built-in to explain the form $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, creating a scalar probability from a vector involves obscuring information.

One may obscure information by even taking a scalar probability, W^*W for a quantum bound state, which exhibits resolution through crests and smoothing it over (creating an envelope function which touches crest peaks) to create the smooth classical probability, $C/v(x) dx$. This is another example of information loss.

In (2), it is suggested that one use the non-relativistic limit of a Dirac 4-spinor, i.e. a two 2-spinor vector: $\{ W, 1/2m \sigma \cdot p W \}$. For a free particle, the vector shows the wavelength \hbar/p , but $W^* \text{total} \cdot W^* \text{total}$ does not like the $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ case. For an infinite well potential, one time averages and so uses $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. This already loses information, but in the Dirac wavefunction approach, the top component goes as $\cos(px)$ if $a(p) = a(-p)$, and the bottom as $\sin(px)$. Thus, even though the two have the same wavelength, there is a phase shift and $W^* \text{total} \cdot W^* \text{total}$ obscures the wavelength. This occurs also in the oscillator case as shown in (2).

We thus conclude that one uses averaging when creating probabilities (even when creating W bound by time averaging $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$), one loses physical information and so must be careful in interpreting such a probability.

References

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